

BEHAVIOUR OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE AND DETERMINATION OF ITS PARACHOR.

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Although the solubility of mercuric chloride in organic solvents and its low conductivity at ordinary temperatures are in favour of co-valent nature of mercuric chloride, yet the fact that mercuric chloride is an inorganic metallic salt and that it has abnormally high temperature coefficient of conductivity and that it has coagulating power like other electrolytes confirm its electrovalent character. From results of boiling point measurement mercuric chloride is believed to form aggregates and that its ionisation may be of a higher order. The results of parachor and Raman-effect do not contradict either views.

The abnormal behaviour of mercuric chloride is well known. Although it is purely an inorganic compound, it is more soluble in certain organic solvents.

Mercuric chloride is a metallic chloride and as such is expected to show a high conductivity in aqueous solution. Faraday (*Phil. Trans.*, 1834, 124, 77; 1838, 128, 83) first established the very low conductivity of mercuric chloride both in solid and molten states. A complete reference to the conductivity work may be found in a paper by Joshi and Solanki (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 617).

In view of this interesting behaviour of mercuric chloride we have tried to see whether determination of parachor throws any light on its constitution. The experimental procedure is the same as in our previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 149). Our results are recorded below.

γ = surface tension of the solution. P_m = parachor of the mixture. P_1 = parachor of the solute. x = molar fraction of the solute. $1-x$ = molar fraction of the solvent. d = density of the mixture.

TABLE I.

Parachor in ethyl alcohol.

Parachor of absolute alcohol = 124.9.

x	Temp.	d .	γ .	P_m .	P_1 .	x	Temp.	d .	γ .	P_m .	P_1 .
0.02592	30°	0.8352	20.82	126.1	201.0	0.02051	30°	0.8640	21.94	126.9	210.4
	50	0.8166	18.62	126.2	207.8	0.02546	40	0.8732	19.20	126.9	208.1
	70	0.7962	16.78	126.1	201.0	0.02783	30	0.8822	21.41	127.6	208.9

TABLE II.

Parachor in methyl alcohol.

Parachor of methyl alcohol = 88.98.

Temp.	d .	γ .	P_m .	P_1 .
35°	0.8608	24.67	90.90	236.5
45	0.8507	23.96	91.21	259.6
60	0.8328	21.89	91.20	259.6

TABLE III.

Parachor in ethyl acetate.

Parachor of ethyl acetate = 213.0.					Parachor of ethyl acetate = 213.0.				
$\alpha = 0.0320$					$\alpha = 0.0358$				
Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .	Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .
30°	0.9587	22.77	214.0	245.9	30°	0.9729	22.78	212.2	191.1
40	0.9491	21.82	213.7	234.4	40	0.9607	21.98	213.0	213.6
60	0.9258	19.08	213.3	221.9	50	0.9449	20.67	213.3	222.0
65	0.9203	18.14	212.9	209.4	$\alpha = 0.0255$.				
$\alpha = 0.03992$.					30°	0.9523	22.45	212.7	203.2
30°	0.9811	22.76	212.2	193.0	50	0.9266	20.22	212.9	210.5
40	0.9690	21.54	212.9	170.4	60	0.9111	18.87	212.8	206.9

TABLE IV.

Parachor in acetone.

Parachor of acetone = 159.6.					Parachor of acetone = 159.6.				
$\alpha = 0.02327$.					$\alpha = 0.04345$.				
Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .	Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .
15°	0.8666	23.62	160.2	210.2	15°	0.9327	24.71	161.0	186.3
20	0.8632	23.09	159.9	163.3	20	0.9274	24.23	160.9	184.1
					25	0.9243	23.69	160.6	177.1

TABLE V

Parachor in pyridine.

Parachor of pyridine = 198.2.

$\alpha = 0.02328$					$\alpha = 0.02328$				
Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .	Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .
30°	1.039	36.34	197.2	154.6	30°	1.029	33.83	197.6	172.8
40	1.030	35.34	197.5	167.6	60	1.008	32.60	197.8	180.4

It is interesting to note that pyridine and mercuric chloride form co-ordination compounds of the type $HgCl_2 \cdot 2 Py$, $HgCl_2 \cdot 4 Py$ etc.

TABLE VI.

Parachor in distilled water.

Parachor of distilled water = 52.89.

$\alpha = 0.004844$.					$\alpha = 0.004199$.				
Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .	Temp.	d.	γ .	P_m .	P_x .
15°	1.054	71.11	52.93	187.8	15°	1.045	69.95	52.77	169.5
35	1.050	70.23	53.00	202.3	45	1.036	67.72	52.79	173.3
45	1.048	69.02	52.98	198.2	55	1.033	67.01	52.82	189.9
55	1.042	67.54	52.90	182.7	75	1.021	66.49	52.91	202.4
75	1.030	64.85	52.93	187.8					

The calculated value of parachor of mercuric chloride is about 180.

Our view (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 225) that when atomic and ionic parachors are the same no idea can be formed as regards amount of ionisation seems to be confirmed from these observations. Ray's work (*ibid.* 1938, 15, 43) suggests smaller values for ionic parachors. Hence, our results indicate low ionisation which supports conductivity results. Our boiling point results, which are given below indicate higher ionisation at boiling point and thus confirm the high temperature coefficient of conductivity for mercuric chloride.

Jone's work (*Carnegie Inst. Washington*, 1907, p. 60) rules out solvation of mercuric chloride. The high molecular weight of mercuric chloride in organic solvent suggests a tendency to complex formation. It is natural therefore to infer that in water also mercuric chloride forms complex aggregates with higher order of ionisation as suggested by Joshi and Solanki (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE VII.

Molecular weight of mercuric chloride.

In H ₂ O		In Et acetate.		In Et.OH.		In MeOH		In pyridine.		In acetone.	
Solvent = 24.95 g.		Solvent = 22.2.		Solvent = 19.46 g.		Solvent = 19.79		Solvent = 24.28 g.		Solvent = 19.42 g.	
K _{solvent} = 320		K _{solvent} = 2790		K _{solvent} = 1150		K _{solvent} = 880		K _{solvent} = 2710		K _{solvent} = 1670	
HgCl ₂	M.W.	HgCl ₂	M.W.	HgCl ₂	M.W.	HgCl ₂	M.W.	HgCl ₂	M.W.	HgCl ₂	M.W.
2.4920 g.	225.7	1.925 g.	302.4	2.8984 g.	305.9	5.1680 g.	302.4	1.5062 g.	329.1	4.6576 g.	336.7
4.6010	245.9	3.3216	294.9	4.7896	298.0	7.0574	285.2	4.5376	304.1	6.2784	323.3
6.1778	247.4	5.6718	295.7	7.2894	293.0	8.3374	278.7	6.4316	296.2	8.2386	314.9
8.0554	258.3	6.9076	289.5								

We have studied the coagulating power of mercuric chloride. The sols employed were those of arsenic sulphide, antimony sulphide and manganese dioxide. In arsenic sulphide the order of coagulating power is Al > Hg > Ba > K. In antimony sulphide the order is the same. However in manganese dioxide sol the order is Ba > Al > Hg. These abnormal results are in accordance with the results obtained by Ganguly and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 28, 70, 836), Dhar, Sen and Ghosh (*ibid.*, 1924, 28, 457), Chakravarty and Dhar (*ibid.*, 1927, 31, 997), Chatterji and Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 83, 18). The high coagulating power of mercuric chloride supports its electrovalent nature.

Mercuric chloride shows Raman line but this does not contradict its electrovalent nature (*cf.* West and Arthur, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 215). Moreover Fajan's rule requires mercuric chloride to be electrovalent.

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